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Country report on Mexico

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Mexico's Macroeconomic Landscape: Analysis and Challenges

Introduction:

Mexico plays a pivotal role in the Latin American region, being the second most populous country and boasting the second largest economy in the area. Globally, it stands as the 14th largest economy in terms of GDP, set apart by its distinctive limited restrictions to trade, facilitated by its many Free Trade Agreements (FTAs), granting Mexico access to 50 countries, and securing the label of one of the most open economies in the world. Mexico has become an increasingly preferable trading partner to the US in recent years, as the advantages of lower-cost trading benefit many US businesses, encouraging nearshoring initiatives.

The following report investigates Mexico's current macroeconomy, highlights its recent economic evolution amidst recent global shocks, and will delve deeper into some of its macroeconomic challenges.

The Current Macroeconomic State of Mexico:

Economic Growth:

Economic growth is an increase in the total value of output produced in an economy over a period of time. It is an increase in Real GDP. In Mexico GDP (Gross domestic product) is measured on a quarterly basis.

Figure 1.1 Mexico GDP vs Brazil (Data Source: The World Bank)

Mexico is the second largest economy in Central America, with a GDP of \$1.47 trillion in 2022, falling behind Brazil which has a GDP of \$1.92 trillion (Shown in Figure 1.1) (The World Bank, 2024). However, due to having a lower population size, Mexico is comparatively in a better macroeconomic state than Brazil, as it has a higher GDP per capita of \$11,497 compared to Brazil's \$8,918 (The World Bank, 2024), suggesting higher living standards in Mexico.

Figure 1.2 Mexico GDP Growth (Data source: The World Bank)

Mexico has had a highly volatile economic growth rate as shown by Figure 1.2. In the last decade, the only major stall of the economy was noticed in 2020 when it shrunk by 8.65%. This was a similar story for most countries as COVID-19 shocked labour forces resulting in many supply shortages. Mexico bounced back early in the third quarter of 2020 with its solid manufacturing base, leading to its most recent growth rate of 3.9% in 2022.

Other noticeable shocks to Mexico's growth, as shown in figure 1.2, are in 2009 due to the financial crisis, and the Mexican Peso crisis in 1994 where GDP had fallen 5.91% by 1995. This was a result of the significant devaluing of the Peso, which resulted in a plummet of the value of exported goods, significantly reducing export revenues, and thus reducing real GDP.

Price Stability:

Inflation is a rise in the average price levels of goods and services in an economy. Inflation in Mexico is measured using the CPI (Consumer Price Index), and the Central Bank of Mexico (Banco de México) has announced an annual inflationary target of 3%.

1.3 Inflation within Mexico (Data Source: The World Bank)

Figure

As shown above, in Figure 1.3, the inflation rate as of 2022 was 7.9%. This is the highest rate of inflation since the turn of the century, and is 4.9% above the target rate, suggesting Mexico's price stability is negatively impacting its current macroeconomic state. As a result, the Central Bank of Mexico raised the base interest rate to 11.25% to bring inflation closer to their target. However, this could hinder Mexico's growth rate as both consumption and investment will decrease.

Mexico's Peso crisis in 1994 resulted in inflation soaring from 6.97% to 35.0%, as the significant decline in the value of the Peso would have made import prices rise dramatically, thus increasing costs of production and therefore rises in price levels.

Unemployment:

Unemployment in Mexico is measured through the ENOE (The National Survey of Occupation and Employment), which provides both monthly and quarterly information regarding the labour market. The ENOE measures both formal and informal labour, informal labour being employment lacking in government regulation or registration.

Figure 1.4 Unemployment Within Mexico (Data Source: The World Bank)

Figure 1.4 maps the total unemployment between 1991 and 2022. It indicates that unemployment in Mexico has fluctuated between 3-7%.

1995 saw a considerable rise in unemployment, due to the Mexican Peso crisis, which happened when the Mexican central bank abruptly devalued the Peso. In order to limit a large outflow of capital, the central bank raised interest rates substantially, resulting in higher costs of borrowing for firms. Devaluation of the Peso also resulted in more expensive imports for firms giving rise to higher costs of production, and eventually leading to firms having to dismiss employees in order to maintain their profits.

The lowest unemployment in the last 30 years occurred when Mexico hosted the FIFA Confederations cup in 1999. Employment wasn't generated solely for the event itself, but also within local businesses- to cater for the influx of tourists in the country.

In the last decade (excluding the rise in unemployment during the pandemic), unemployment has been steadily falling. This is likely a direct result of various employment schemes which the Ministry of Labour and Employment Promotion of Mexico City (styFE) have implemented to tackle unemployment, with a particular focus on the youth of Mexico.

One scheme which has been implemented to boost employment is the ‘Jóvenes Construyendo el Futuro’ (Youth Building the Future) program, which is aimed at assisting 18- to 29-year-olds, who are not currently in education, or employed. The program delivers job training in a local work centre, in addition to a monthly stipend, and medical insurance. Since its establishment in 2019, the program has helped over 2.8 million young people ([Government of Mexico, 2023](#)).

The Current account:

The current account is a record of a country’s transactions with the rest of the world. The current account balance is equal to; Value of exports – value of imports + Net investment.

As shown in figure 1.5 below, Mexico has been running a current account deficit for four years up to 2022, meaning the country's capital outflows are greater than their capital inflows.

Figure 1.5 Current Account Balances (Data Source: The World Bank)

Figure 1.5 compares Mexico’s Current account balance with that of the USA, Mexico’s largest trading partner. The graph illustrates that the fluctuations experienced by the countries are virtually the inverse of one another. This likely stems from the strong trade partnership between the two countries, enabled through initiatives such as the USMCA (United States- Mexico- Canada Agreement) which allows for freer trade between membership countries - directly linking their current accounts.

When exports within Mexico grow, their current account is likely to move towards a surplus. In 2021, 78.06% of Mexico’s exports went to the USA ([WITS, 2021](#)). Therefore, growth in Mexican exports implies a corresponding increase in USA imports, which would lead to a current account deficit, contributing to opposing current account balances. The same is true

for the inverse, as when Mexico's imports grow, the USA's exports would be expected to grow too, as 43.69% of Mexico's total imports are from the USA ([WITS](#), 2021).

Imports and exports are a large portion of a country's current account balance. Figure 1.6 shows that within Mexico, imports are generally greater than exports. The data also shows that both variables have been increasing relatively steadily for the last 40 years.

Figure 1.6 Mexico's Imports and Exports (Data Source: [World Bank](#))

The steady growth in imports and exports can, to a large extent, be attributed to Mexico's membership in international trade agreements such as the USMCA and the ALADI, which reduce or eliminate trade barriers between member countries, enabling freer trade, and widening the scope of partners to trade with.

Mexico's recent economic evolution:

How it has dealt with recent global shocks:

Mexico, having in recent years abandoned protectionist policies such as import substitution industrialisation, has opened its borders to international trade and thereby also increased the level of global economic integration maintained by the country. Trade liberalisation in Mexico has occurred via various strategies such as the creation of multilateral trading agreement NAFTA alongside the United States and Canada in 1994 and, more recently, the opening up of Mexico's financial markets. These liberalisation policies have effectively linked the Mexican economy with the global economy, thereby also making the country more susceptible to the effects of global economic shocks (Robert. A Blecker, 2009).

The approaches undertaken by Mexico in tackling such macroeconomic shocks have varied over time, and policies implemented in response to more recent shocks can be assessed through analysing older strategies, and hence also demonstrating the economic evolution of the country. For example, Mexico's response to the 1980 debt crisis, which, as noted by Ros J. (1987), was seen by other countries to be 'a demonstration of how to get out of the crisis', yet still left the country 'in continuous economic and financial troubles', can be used as an example of how Mexico has utilised past experiences to shape their policy responses over

time, even eventually paving the way for how the Mexican economy has dealt with the most recent economic effects of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The 1982 crisis succeeded an oil boom, occurring between 1978-1981, which relaxed Mexico's balance of payments' constraints on growth, leading to a period of economic expansion. This rapid expansion was however also associated with increased financial vulnerability and uncertainty, contributing to the eventual 1982 crisis. Furthermore, during the 1970s, Latin American borrowing from US banks increased drastically, with by 1982 total outstanding debt from all sources totalling \$327 billion (FDIC 1997). Servicing debt can ultimately come at the expense of productive investment and growth for a country, and thus would have inhibited Mexico's capacity for economic expansion in this period, which subsequently is often referred to as the 'lost decade'.

Figure 2.1 Government Expenditure, % of GDP (Data Source: IMF Datamapper (2023))

Eventually, as Mexican policy response efforts were futile, an 'international lender of last resort' rescue effort between commercial banks, central banks, and the IMF was initiated, with Mexico alongside the other LDCs involved agreeing to undertake structural reforms of their economies and eliminate budget deficits in return for a restructuring of the accumulated debt. Mexico has since maintained a conscientious effort, as seen on Figure 2.1 & Figure 2.2, to keep government expenditure as a % of GDP fairly low in order to work towards a balanced government budget, and general government debt as a % of GDP consistent (sitting at around 40% of GDP until recently). This approach has further been maintained in response to global shocks, for example being showcased through the level of crisis spending which occurred during COVID sitting only at around 3% of GDP, in order to 'avoid massive government debt issuance' (Manual Hoyos, 2020).

Figure 2.2 General government debt, as % of GDP (Data Source: OECD (2023))

We can use the model $AD = c_0 + c_1(1 - \tau)Y + I r + G - mY + X$, where AD represents Aggregate demand and is made up of c_0 (autonomous consumption), c_1 (marginal propensity to consume), τ (tax rates), Y (domestic production), $I r$ (investment multiplied by interest rate), G (Government spending), m (marginal propensity to import), and X (exports) in order to understand the effect of government spending in easing fluctuations and aggregate demand shocks within the economy. Although keeping spending low is important in avoiding further debt crises, this strategy is also not best in accelerating economic recovery after a dip following a shock. This stems from the idea that if government spending remains low, expansions in AD are less likely. This is demonstrated through the Mexican economy's stance choosing not to increase public debt to boost fiscal expenditures in response to the COVID-19 shock, and as a result suffering, according to the Bank of Mexico, 'the greatest contraction ever recorded of holdings of emerging economies' (Manual Hoyos, 2020).

This idea of the influence of the different factors affecting Aggregate demand on the demand side of an economy can be represented using the multiplier plot:

This diagram can be used to illustrate how, for example, a fall in autonomous consumption due to a global shock like those faced by Mexico, can be rectified by injections into the economy. A fall in autonomous consumption would lead to AD falling from AD_0 to AD_1 . On the other hand, an increase in Government spending would be able to push AD levels up to AD_2 according to the multiplier effect - a greater multiplier effect will require smaller levels of government spending.

COVID-19's Impact on Mexico's Economy:

The Covid 19 pandemic undoubtedly had a negative impact on Mexico's economy, despite progressive structural reforms following NAFTA; which saw improvements in globalisation, efficiency, and the trade balance. This also meant that regulation was increased, thus labour rights, workplace safety, environmental protection, and regulation concerning wage exploitation, were all improved too. The pre-pandemic economy was already struggling in comparison to the US (Mexico's largest trading partner) whose economy grew in 2019 whilst Mexico's shrunk - predominantly caused by unsuccessful fiscal decisions and less investment; negatively affecting business and consumer confidence nationwide. This 'took the private sector by surprise (i.e. the cancellation of a \$13 billion airport project)' which was due in the capital city (L Sandin, 2020). The pandemic had detrimental effects on the country's lowest income households: following Covid, the very poorest households received a 'modest recovery package', and others received no support whatsoever.

In July of 2020, the death count due to Covid 'surpassed 46,000 - making it the third highest in the world. However, with contractionary fiscal policy in place, government debt remained low. The economic state of Mexico in 2020 was not set up for adequate responses to the pandemic, facing challenges in a political, public health, and public safety sense. By just August of 2020, Mexico faced a death rate of 14% with around half a million cases.

Unemployment inevitably rose during this period, particularly because the majority of the population work in the informal sector - where there is an absence of formal employment. Consequently, the informal sector workers have lacked access to unemployment benefits from the government. These workers also do not contribute to tax revenue, therefore posing an issue of lack of government funding. This increase in unemployment can be seen in Figure 2.3 - where pre-pandemic unemployment as a percentage of total labour force (national estimate) peaks in 2020 at 4.441%, from 2018 at 3.275%, and sees a recovery back to 3.256% by 2022. Mexico managed to keep unemployment under control in some aspects, especially in comparison to the US which went from 3.3896% (2018) to 8.055% in 2020.

Figure 2.3 Unemployment (% of total labour force) (Data Source: The World Bank)

With higher unemployment, crime rates often increase subsequently, and in Mexico the government has struggled continuously to enforce laws and take action towards illegal markets, such as drug cartels putting public safety at risk (M Leroux-Parra, 2020). During 2020, Mexico recorded one of its 'most violent days of the year', June 7th which saw 117 murders, and is causal to cartels exploiting the lack of security thanks to the pandemic, as well as to expand their dominance throughout the country and its industries. Since 2006, when the president at the time declared a 'war on drugs', the rate of intentional homicides has increased fourfold.

Impact of the Ukraine war on Mexico's Economy:

A more current economic shock which Mexico has had to deal with is the Ukraine war. Mexico's response started in choosing to remain 'neutral', which changed when the president declared its opposition to the US and European nations providing support and arms to Ukraine, and they refused to adhere to imposing sanctions on Russia. However, they did not support Russian actions, but it is likely the Mexican government felt it was unnecessary, as their bilateral trade was relatively low in 2021, amounting to less than \$3bn in 2021.

The inflationary effect on all economies worldwide would also be experienced in Mexico as goods (specifically fuel and oil) become more expensive. This inhibits economic activity to thrive in the recovery from Covid, as Mexico becomes more integrated in global trade markets. Higher oil prices could in turn raise government revenue and boost nearshoring (defined as the practice of transferring a business operation to a nearby country) as trade with Mexico becomes even more preferable to the US, in terms of lower costs - thus boosting FDIs and in turn aggregate demand and GDP.

Long/Short Term Macroeconomic Problem: Low Productivity Growth in Mexico

Brief Introduction

Over the past 30 years, Mexico has achieved an average GDP growth of around 2.23% since 1990 (The World Bank Data). However, relative to other comparable emerging economies, the GDP growth rate of Mexico has been significantly, and consistently, lower. In this section, we argue that a key contributing factor is the low levels of productivity growth.

GDP and Productivity Growth - Mexico and Other Emerging Economies

In Figure 3.1 below, the evolution of GDP per capita (relative to the US, and adjusted for purchasing power parity) is shown for a range of representative countries (characterised as emerging economies) from regions around the world including Europe, Asia and South America.

In general, the graph shows that all of these countries (except for Mexico) have made progress towards closing the gap in GDP per capita relative to the US. For example, during the period from 1990 to 2017, Chile increased its GDP per capita relative to the US from just over 0.2 to around 0.4, a 100% increase. Meanwhile, the GDP per capita of Mexico relative to the US has remained constant, and more recently has even experienced a marginal decline.

Figure 3.1. GDP/Capita (Relative to USA) (Data Source: The World Bank)

There are several potential reasons as to why a country may fail to achieve higher (or comparably high) GDP growth rates. As an emerging economy, and as indicated above, we would expect Mexico to be closing the gap in GDP per capita relative to the US. In this section, we argue that the principal reason for Mexico's stubbornly-low relative GDP growth rate is its failure to significantly improve its levels of industrial productivity.

Furthermore, we suggest that Mexico has achieved its positive levels of GDP growth, mainly through labour accumulation, rather than, for example, investing in skills improvement or capital equipment. However, as Mexico reaches a level where it no longer makes financial sense for firms to hire more labour due to decreasing returns to scale in labour, the country will be forced to invest in human capital and/or machinery in order to maintain sustainable levels of GDP growth.

Indeed, the phenomenon of lower increases in productivity due to Mexico's low-skilled economy reaching its natural level of employment has already been observed over the last decade. In Figure 3.2 below, we observe that Mexico has seen an overall gradual decrease in GDP growth (following a ten year moving average) - with 7.5% in 1980 and having plateaued at 2.5% after 2010. One may argue, therefore, that it is fundamentally important for Mexico to increase its economic productivity in order to achieve sustainable levels in GDP growth.

Figure 3.2. Mexico's Declining GDP Growth (Data Source: The World Bank)

In the next part, we explore how the so-called 'informal economy' contributes to the low productivity of Mexico's economy and why Mexico has fallen behind other emerging economies.

Financial Exclusion - the Informal Economy and Impact on Productivity:

A significant part of the Mexican economy is characterised as 'informal' - 55.0% of the workforce are paid for work without any formal employment contract being in place (INEGI, 2023).

With an economy that has a high demand for low-skilled, low-wage labour (with little to no educational requirements), and where the administration costs associated with 'formalising' employment would be a significant economic disincentive, it is clear why informal employment is so predominant.

Indeed, with high levels of bureaucracy, it is often easier for 'formal' firms to hire workers illegally in order to avoid payroll taxes, severance payments and other costs (Diaz, 2023). As a consequence, many of these businesses face significant barriers in accessing financial services, which, in turn, has led to the excessive labour accumulation instead of capital accumulation.

Furthermore, low investment rates, particularly in public infrastructure, have held back sectors such as telecommunications and transportation and have been a leading cause for Mexico's low economic growth compared to other rapidly growing emerging economies (Iacovone, Moreno, Olaberria, López, 2022).

Informal firms have a tendency to be less productive than their formal counterparts. These firms are less able to innovate, adapt to advanced technologies and integrate into global value chains (GVC). This dynamic, coupled with a large concentration of Mexican firms in the manufacturing and service sectors, which are very capable of hiring informally, has hindered aggregate productivity growth (Iacovone et al, 2022).

Gross Fixed Capital Formation refers to the total value of investments in physical assets like machinery, equipment, buildings, and infrastructure that are used for production purposes

within an economy. With reference to the graph, Figure 3.3 below, we observe that Mexico lies behind other countries with emerging economies such as Malaysia, Korea and Indonesia. On the other hand, it does not differ too much from other South American countries. This lower level of investment can be closely linked to poor productivity growth and informal firms having a lack of access to financial instruments which would help them grow and become more productive.

Figure 3.3 Gross Fixed Capital Formation (Data Source: The World Bank)

Financial Exclusion - Lack of Access to Credit

The difficulties in accessing credit is a key reason why investment levels have been so low. Access to credit is a key driver of productivity growth, as credit allows for businesses to spend beyond their current financial means and repay later. This can allow for investment in research and development practices. This helps stimulate innovation, allowing for businesses to find ways which they can produce more efficiently at a lower unit cost, hence improving their productivity. However, in Mexico a lack of access to credit has held back innovation. Domestic credit to the private sector was just 39%, compared to the OECD average of 161% in 2020, representing a significant difference to nations at similar levels of development.

A key determinant of whether a firm will be able to access credit in Mexico is their level of collateral. If a firm has a high value of collateral, banks can seize assets if a firm defaults on their loan to cover it. This means that banks will offer lower interest rates on loans to firms with valuable collateral. This creates an issue for smaller Mexican firms looking to grow. In Mexico, smaller firms are 9% more likely to be unable to finance needed investment due to a lack of access to finance (Iacovone, Moreno, Olaberria, Lopez, 2022). To expand and increase productivity, smaller firms need credit for investment. However, smaller firms tend

to lack collateral, so banks see lending money to them as risky. This results in high interest rates being offered and more expensive borrowing, which smaller firms won't be able to afford, meaning that they don't invest and stay unproductive. Furthermore, if smaller firms aren't growing, then there is a lack of competitive pressure on larger firms and this creates a disincentive to innovate, causing a lack of productivity growth across the economy as observed in Mexico.

The over-importance of collateral in Mexico's financial markets causes a misallocation of funds away from more productive firms who spend credit on R&D (which is not collateralizable in the short term) and towards those less productive firms who may own valuable assets that have limited productivity gains (real estate). To innovate, firms need large amounts of investment so they need to borrow large amounts. Using the above analysis, the more productive firms who lack collateral will be charged higher interest, thus unable to borrow and invest as much, withholding productivity rises.

The seven largest banks in Mexico hold 78% market share (trade.gov, 2023). This indicates price setting power among these firms. This hinders an efficient allocation of credit in Mexico, with banks focusing on profitable market segments and having price setting capabilities to charge higher interest rates to firms without collateral. If the industry was more competitive, banks would be more willing to take risks with loans, or else face lower profits. This could result in cheaper loans being offered to firms without collateral, which could stimulate innovation and productivity gains.

With this said, in the last few years Fintech innovations, such as CoDi, have permitted Mexican businesses to operate with greater security and efficiency, reducing unit costs. This is a clear example of a measure in line with helping achieve the National Financial inclusion strategy (2020) which has helped productivity growth. However, it is clear that if the Mexican government can reform policy in the banking industry to foster competition, firms will have greater access to loans, creating innovation and stimulating strong productivity gains in the future.

In conclusion, slow productivity growth represents a major challenge to Mexico's continued economic development. With GDP growth declining (see fig 3.2), the Mexican government must address the major productivity issue going forwards. The earlier part of our section found that growth in Mexico has been predominantly driven by labour accumulation rather than capital accumulation. Furthermore, significantly lower capital investment (relative to other emerging economies) is exacerbating the productivity growth in Mexico. We now also understand that the extent of financial exclusion has driven low investment levels in Mexico preventing capital being accumulated. A fiscal stimulus or a reforming of competition policy in the banking sector are examples of policy recommendations that could help boost investment, and solve this issue going forwards.

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